

***Conura xanthostigma* (DALMAN, 1820) new to the Polish fauna with new records of some chalcid wasps previously recorded in Poland (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea, Chalcididae)**

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2615627>

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ABSTRACT. *Conura xanthostigma* (DALMAN, 1820) new to the Polish fauna with new records of some chalcid wasps previously recorded in Poland (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea, Chalcididae).

The Chalcididae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) is one of the smallest chalcid wasp families in the Polish fauna as far as the number of recorded species. So far, the occurrence of twelve species has been documented. So far, all the species are known from only a few localities in the country. In the present study the list is updated with another taxon, namely *Conura xanthostigma* (DALMAN, 1820). Also, new localities are presented for the following species: *Brachymeria femorata* (PANZER, 1801), *Brachymeria minuta* (LINNAEUS, 1767), *Brachymeria parvula* (WALKER, 1834), *Brachymeria tibialis* (WALKER, 1834), *Chalcis biguttata* SPINOLA, 1808, *Chalcis sispes* (LINNAEUS, 1761), *Haltichella rufipes* (OLIVIER, 1791), and *Hockeria bifasciata* WALKER, 1834.

KEY WORDS: Hymenoptera, Chalcidoidea, Chalcididae, *Conura xanthostigma*, new records, Poland.

INTRODUCTION

The family Chalcididae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) is one of the smallest chalcid wasp families in the Polish fauna as far as the number of recorded species. There are ca. 1500 species described in the world fauna, distributed primarily in the tropics. The wasps are mainly primary endoparasitoids of Lepidoptera and Diptera, but a few species utilize larvae of Coleoptera, Hymenoptera or Neuroptera (GIBSON 1993, GAULD & BOLTON 1996, NOYES 2018).

The first records on Polish chalcid wasps were published by the end of 19th century by BRISCHKE (1881, 1888, 1889) who mentioned only *Brachymeria minuta* (as *Chalcis minuta*) from former West Prussia (now in Poland). Later, after almost 80 years it was Zdenek Bouček and Henryk Szczepański who contributed significantly to the knowledge of the family in Poland (BOUČEK 1952, SZCZEPAŃSKI 1959, 1968). Some information on the family members were also published by NIKOLSKAJA (1960), NOSKIEWICZ & PUŁAWSKI (1974), WIĄCKOWSKI (1978), MICZULSKI (1980) and KOLK (1982).

The first checklist of Polish Chalcididae was published by WIŚNIEWSKI (1997). The list was then updated by a few papers announcing new species for the Polish fauna

(WIŚNIEWSKI & DOBOSZ 1998, WIŚNIEWSKI 2007, KLEJDYSZ & WENDZONKA 2017). The observations of the family members are rare, and all the species records published until now come from only a few localities in the country.

The aims of the paper are: to update the list of Polish chalcid wasps, at least partly fill the gap in our knowledge of the distribution of Chalcididae in Poland, and to present images of selected species.

So far, the occurrence of twelve species has been documented in published papers. In the present study the list is updated with another taxon, namely *Conura xanthostigma* (DALMAN, 1820). Also, new localities are presented for the following species: *Brachymeria femorata* (PANZER, 1801), *Brachymeria minuta* (LINNAEUS, 1767), *Brachymeria parvula* (WALKER, 1834), *Brachymeria tibialis* (WALKER, 1834), *Chalcis biguttata* SPINOLA, 1808, *Chalcis sispes* (LINNAEUS, 1761), *Haltichella rufipes* (OLIVIER, 1791), and *Hockeria bifasciata* WALKER, 1834.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The research on the family Chalcididae in Poland carried by the authors started some time ago (the studies have been carried out for more than 25 years now) and due to scarcity of material it is rather of the type of an 'extensive' project. The specimens were mainly collected during studies on other groups of Hymenoptera as well as inventories of specific regions in Poland. The specimens were collected with an entomological sweep net on herbs/bushes, tree leaves, but also with the use of pan traps.

Apart from that, some collections in scientific institutions were also studied (Upper Silesian Museum in Bytom, University of Łódź, Wigierski National Park). Some specimens were also loaned for study by private collectors. Materials collected by the senior author (B. Wiśniowski) are housed in his private collection; the collection includes also specimens collected or reared by M. Borowiec, J. Dąbrowski, J. Gutowski, A. Kostro-Ambroziak, J.K. Kowalczyk, A. Krzysztofiak, P. Olszewski, H. Piekarska-Boniecka, B. and M. Soszyński, K. Szczepko). The Upper Silesian Museum in Bytom houses the specimens collected by the second author (W. Żyła), as well as of some other collectors (R. Dobosz, S. Skrabania).

The species are listed in alphabetical order and the names follow NOYES (2018). Most specimens were collected by the senior author (in the list below as BW). The zoogeographical regions are ordered after BURAKOWSKI *et al.* (1971). Within each region the localities are ordered alphabetically after UTM coordinates. The photographs were taken with the use of stereoscopic zoom microscope Nikon SMZ 1500 and DS-Fi2 colour camera head. Question mark '?' in the text below means, that some information was unavailable, e.g. name of a collector, day, month, etc. In the list below the abbreviations should be read as follows: **NP** – National Park, **LP** – Landscape Park, **Res.** – Nature Reserve.

RESULTS

During the studies the following taxon was recorded as new to Polish fauna:

Conura xanthostigma (DALMAN, 1820)

The species was recorded on two localities:

Kraków-Wieluń Upland: [CA97] Klucze, 11.08.2014 – 1 ♀ on the edge of ‘Błędów Desert’, on flowers of Apiaceae, leg. W. Żyła,

Małopolska Upland: [DA27] Rzeżuśnia by Gołcza, 26.07.2006 – 1 ♂ in *Inuletum ensifoliae* plant community on chalk, leg. BW.

Distributed from Western Europe to Russian Far East and China, Canada and India (NOYES 2018). In larval stage *Conura xanthostigma* is primary ectoparasitoid of sawflies larvae of the genus *Arge* SCHRANK, 1802 (Hymenoptera: Argidae); the host larvae are phytophages on *Rosa* sp. Imagines are easy recognizable after body colouration (Fig. 1) and the shape of hind legs (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Male of *Conura xanthostigma* (DALMAN, 1820) (photo B. Wiśniowski).

Ryc. 1. Samiec *Conura xanthostigma* (DALMAN, 1820) (fot. B. Wiśniowski).

Fig. 2. Hind leg of female of *Comura xanthostigma* (DALMAN, 1820) (photo B. Wiśniowski).

Ryc. 2. Tylna noga samicy *Comura xanthostigma* (DALMAN, 1820) (fot. B. Wiśniowski).

Fig. 3. Female of *Brachymeria femorata* (PANZER, 1801); body length 8 mm. (photo B. Wiśniowski).

Ryc. 3. Samica *Brachymeria femorata* (PANZER, 1801); dł. ciała 8 mm. (fot. B. Wiśniowski).

New localities of species previously recorded from Poland:

Brachymeria femorata (PANZER, 1801) (Fig. 3)

Listed from Poland for the first time by BOUČEK (1952). Included in the checklist of Polish Chalcididae (WIŚNIEWSKI 1997). Some additional records were given by WIŚNIEWSKI (1996, 2007, 2016). New records:

Baltic Coast: [CF44] Gdynia, Klub Tenisowy 'Arka', 30.09.2013 – 1♀, leg. B. Soszyński.

Kraków-Wieluń Upland: [CB72] Olsztyn, Góra Biakło, 04.08.2011 – 1♀ in psammophilous grassland, leg. BW; [CB72] Góry Towarne, 26.07.2012 – 1♂ on flowers of *Libanotis*, leg. BW; [CB90] Skąty Rzędkowickie, 05.08.2011 – 1♀ & 1♂ in xerothermophilous grassland, leg. BW; [DA16] Ojcowski NP, Ojców, 15.03.2008 – 1♀, leg. BW.

Małopolska Upland: [CC40] Góry Wapienne by Burzenin, 02.08.2007 – 1♀, leg. J. K. Kowalczyk; [DA28] 'Biała Góra' Res. by Tunel, 02.08.2012 – 1♂, xerothermophilous grassland on chalk, leg. BW; [DA68] 'Krzyżanowice' Res., 25.07.2006 – 1♀ on flowers of *Pastinaca sativa*, 20.07.2007 – 2♂♂ in a grassland with *Stipa capillata*, leg. BW; [DA69] Góry Pińczowskie Zachodnie, 24.07.2006 – 1♀ & 1♂ on flowers of *Daucus carota*, 09.07.2007 – 2♂♂ on flowers of *Senecio vulgaris*, leg. BW; [DB25] Przedborski LP, 'Murawy Dobromierskie' Res., 27.05.2005 – 1♀, leg. B. Soszyński; [DC40] Spalski LP, Gielzów, 09.05.2009 – 1♀, leg. M. Soszyński; [DC40] Spalski LP, Teofilów, 03.08.2003 – 1♀, leg. B. Soszyński; [EB41] Samborzec, 30.05.2008 – 1♀; [EB51] 'Góry Pieprzowe' Res., 2.08.2008 – 1♀, 13.08.2008 – 2♂♂ – all in grassland on loess, leg. BW.

Mazovian Lowland: [DC69] Kampinoski NP, Bieliny, 26.08.2000 – 2♀♀ on a wooden building, leg. K. Szczepko; [EC10] Radom, Nowa Wola, 12.09.2003 – 1♀, leg. M. Miłkowski.

Roztocze: [FA49] Józefów vicinity, 08.07.2006 – 1♂, clear-cut in pine forest, leg. BW.

Upper Silesia: [CA57] Bytom Szombierki, Park Fazaniec 09.08.2003 – 1♂ on leaves of *Syringa vulgaris*, leg. W. Żyła; [CB31] Lubliniec, 02.06.1996 – 1♀, 29.06.1999 – 1♀, 30.07.1999 – 1♂, leg. R. Dobosz.

Brachymeria minuta (LINNAEUS, 1767)

Listed from Poland for the first time by BRISCHKE (1881, 1888, 1889), and later by SZCZEPAŃSKI (1959) and MICZULSKI (1980). Included in the checklist of Polish Chalcididae (WIŚNIEWSKI 1997). Some additional records were given by WIŚNIEWSKI (1996, 2007, 2016). New records:

Baltic Coast: [CF37] Władysławowo, 07.06.1993 – 1♀, leg. R. Dobosz; [CF44] Gdynia, Klub Tenisowy 'Arka', 18.08.2013 – 1♀, leg. J. K. Kowalczyk.

Mazurian Lakeland: [FE09] Puszcza Augustowska, ???.?.1991 – 1♀ & 2♂♂, leg. ?

Mazovian Lowland: [DC59] Kampinoski NP, Bromierzyk, 10.08.2004 – 1♀, leg. K. Szczepko.

Upper Silesia: [CA57] Bytom-Szombierki, 15.08.2004 – 1♀, leg. W. Żyła.

Kraków-Wieluń Upland: [DA16] Ojcowski NP, Grodzisko, 08.08.2002 – 1♀, 19.08.2002 – 1♀ in grassland on limestone, leg. BW.

Małopolska Upland: [CC93] Łódź-Stoki, 31.08.2003 – 1♀, leg. J. K. Kowalczyk; [DA27] Gołcza, 15.06.2002 – 1♀, on flowers of *Anthriscus* sp., leg. BW; [DA27] Rzeżuśnia by Gołcza, 26.07.2006 – 6♀♀, 10.06.2008 – 1♀, 08.07.2008 – 3♀♀, 08.08.2008 – 1♀,

26.08.2008 – 1♀, 11.09.2008 – 2♀♀, 14.07.2011 – 2♀♀ – all in *Inuletum ensifoliae* plant community on chalk, leg. BW; [DA69] Góry Pińczowskie Zachodnie, 24.07.2006 – 1♀, 9.07.2007 – 2♀♀, in grassland on chalk, leg. BW; [DA78] ‘Skorocice’ Res., 26.07.2006 – 1♀ on flowers of *Daucus carota*, leg. BW; [DA79] ‘Krzyżanowice’ Res., 13.07.2006 – 1♀, 25.07.2006 – 1♀, 20.07.2007 – 2♀♀ – all in grassland community with *Stipa capillata*, leg. BW; [DA87] Ostoja Górecka, Górki, 03.09.2016 – 1♀, on flowers of *Heracleum sphondylium*, leg. BW; [DC03] Łódź, Byszewy, 22.08.1994 – 1♀, [DC03] Łódź, Pomorska str., 11.08.1996 – 1♀, leg. J. K. Kowalczyk; [DC23] Słotwiny, 10.08.1992 – 1♀, leg. E. Ambrozik; [EB51] ‘Góry Pieprzowe’ Res., 02.08.2008 – 3♀♀ in grassland on loess, leg. BW.

Brachymeria parvula (WALKER, 1834) (Fig. 4)

Recorded from Poland in the checklist of Hymenoptera of Ojcowski NP (Wiśniowski 2016). New records:

Mazurian Lakeland: [FE38] Wigierski NP, Zatoka Słupiańska, 18.07.2001 – 1♀, leg. W. Żyła; [FE38] Wigierski NP, Rosochaty Róg, 01.07.2003 – 3♀♀, leg. W. Żyła; [FE38] Wigierski NP, Krzywe, 27.07.2001 – 1♀, leg. A. Krzysztofiak, 27.07.2001 – 2♀♀, leg. W. Żyła; [FF02] ‘Puszcza Romincka’ LP, Żytkiejmy, 22.06.2002 – 1♀, leg. A. Krzysztofiak.

Kraków-Wieluń Upland: [CB90] Włodowice, 26.07.2012 – 1♀ on flowers of *Heracleum sphondylium*, leg. BW.

Małopolska Upland: [DA27] Rzeżuśnia by Gołcza, 26.07.2006 – 1♀ in *Inuletum ensifoliae* plant community on chalk, leg. BW; [DA69] Góry Pińczowskie Zachodnie, 09.07.2007 – 1♀, leg. BW.

Fig. 4. Female of *Brachymeria parvula* (WALKER, 1834); body length 5 mm. (photo B. Wiśniowski).

Ryc. 4. Samica *Brachymeria parvula* (WALKER, 1834); dł. ciała 5 mm. (fot. B. Wiśniowski).

***Brachymeria tibialis* (WALKER, 1834)**

The taxon was recorded as new to Poland by WIŚNIEWSKI (1996, 1997) as *Brachymeria intermedia* (NEES, 1834). Additional records were published from Bieszczady Mts (WIŚNIEWSKI 2000). New records:

Wielkopolska-Kujawy Lowland: [VT84] Gębice, 10.07.2011 – 1♂, leg. J. Wendzonka.

Upper Silesia: [BA99] Ligota Dolna by Strzelce Opolskie, 01–10.07.1967 – 2♀♀ reared from pupae of *Zygaena carniolica*, 21–31.07.1967 – 1♂, leg. et cult. S. Skrabania.

Kraków-Wieluń Upland: [CA97] Klucze, 5–10.08.1968 – 1♀ and 21.08.1968 – 1♀ ex pupae of *Zygaena carniolica*, leg. et cult. ??, 10.07.1972 – 1♂ ex pupae of *Zygaena lonicerae*, leg. et cult. J. Dąbrowski; [CA98] Kwaśniów, 08.08.1968 – 3♀♀ reared from pupae of *Zygaena carniolica*, leg. ??; [CB72] Olsztyn, Góra Biakło, 04.08.2011 – 1♂ in psammophilous grassland; [CB46] Lisowice, 08.08.2001 – 1♀, leg. J. K. Kowalczyk; [CB72] Góry Towarne, 4.08.2011 – 1♀, 12.08.2011 – 5♀♀ & 1♂, 11.07.2012 – 3♂♂, 26.07.2012 – 1♀ & 2♂♂, 01.08.2012 – 4♀♀ – all on flowers of *Libanotis montana*, leg. BW; [CB81] Mirów, 01.08.2012 – 2♂♂ in psammophilous grassland, leg. BW; [DA14] Mydlniki, 11–12.08.1968 – 3♂♂ reared from pupae of *Zygaena carniolica*, leg. et cult. J. Dąbrowski; [DA14] Tyniec Podgórci, 29.08.1965 – 2♂♂ reared from pupae of *Zygaena angelicae*, leg. et cult. J. Dąbrowski; [DA16] Ojcowski NP, Grodzisko, 12.08.1969 – 1♂, 10.08.1969 – 1♂ reared from pupae of *Zygaena* sp., 29.07.1969 – 1♀ from pupae of *Zygaena angelicae*, leg. et cult. J. Dąbrowski; [DA16] buffer zone of Ojcowski NP: Małesowa Skała, 24.07.1994 – 1♀ in *Origano-Brachypodietum*, leg. BW; [DA16] Ojcowski NP, Ojców, 12.09.1995 – 1♀ on wooden building, leg. BW; [DA16] Ojcowski NP, Peperówka, 24.07.2003 – 1♂, leg. BW; [DA16] Ojcowski NP, Pilny Dół, 10.06.2003 – 1♀, leg. BW; [DA16] Ojcowski NP, Skały Węzie, 22.08.2005 – 1♀, leg. BW.

Małopolska Upland: [DA27] Rzeżuśnia by Golcza, 14.07.2011 – 1♀ in *Inuletum ensifoliae* plant community on chalk, leg. BW; [DA47] Klonów 01–10.08.1962 – 2♀♀ & 6♂♂ reared from pupae of *Zygaena angelicae*, leg. et cult. J. Dąbrowski; [DA47] ‘Wały’ Res. by Raclawice, 22.06.2006 – 1♀ in grassland on chalk, leg. BW; [DA69] Góry Pińczowskie Zachodnie, 14.07.2006 – 1♂, 09.07.2007 – 1♂ on flowers of *Daucus carota*, leg. BW; [DA78] ‘Skorocice’ Res., 26.07.2006 – 1♂ on flowers of *Daucus carota*, leg. BW; [DC03] Plichtów, 22.06.2004 – 1♀, leg. J. K. Kowalczyk; [DC14] Dąbrówka Mała, 19.06.2005 – 1♀, leg. J. K. Kowalczyk; [DC36] ‘Polana Siwica’ Res., 15.07.2006 – 1♂, leg. J. K. Kowalczyk; [EB51] ‘Góry Pieprzowe’ Res., 13.08.2008 – 1♂, grassland on loess, leg. BW; [DA69] ‘Polana Polichno’ Res., 14.08.2008 – 1♂ on flowers of Apiaceae, leg. BW.

Roztocze: [FA49] Józefów vicinity, ?? .07.1978 – 1♀, leg. B. Soszyński.

Eastern Beskidy Mts: [DA93] Szczepanowice, 25.08.2003 – 1♀ on wooden building, leg. W. Żyła.

***Chalcis sispes* (LINNAEUS, 1761)**

Recorded from Poland for the first time by WIŚNIEWSKI & DOBOSZ (1998). New records:

Mazurian Lakeland: [FE38] Wigierski NP, Krzywe, 09.06.2000 – 1♀, leg. A. Krzysztofiak; [FF11] Suwalski LP, Turtul, 5.07.1997 – 1♀, leg. R. Dobosz.

Wielkopolska-Kujawy Lowland: [CD48] Koniczynka by Toruń, 18.06.1952 – 1♀, leg. Kosicki.

Mazovian Lowland: [EB08] Radom-Potkanów, 2.08.2016 – 1♂, leg. M. Miłkowski.

Podlasie: [FE37] Rospuda 1.07.2016 – 1♂, leg. A. Kostro-Ambroziak.

Upper Silesia: [CA58] Świerklaniec, 24.07.2006 – 1♀, leg. W. Żyła.

Małopolska Upland: [DB14] Barycz, 21.07.1944 – 1♀, leg. F. Parre’.

Haltichella rufipes (OLIVIER, 1791)

Listed from Poland for the first time by SZCZEPAŃSKI (1959). Included in the checklist of Polish Chalcididae (WIŚNIEWSKI 1997). Additional records were given by WIŚNIEWSKI (2007). New records:

Wielkopolska-Kujawy Lowland: [XT29] Wielkopolski NP, Grabina, 09.10.2006 – 1♀ in oak-hornbeam forest, leg. H. Piekarska-Boniecka; [XT61] Milicz, 25.08.2007 – 3♀♀ in an old park, leg. M. Borowiec; [XT61] Ruda Miłicka, 12–19.07.2006 – 2♀♀, leg. M. Borowiec; [XU30] Poznań, 10–20.08.2003 – 1♂, leg. H. Piekarska-Boniecka; [XU32] Biedrusko, 23.08.2004 – 1♀, 29.08.2005 – 1♀, leg. H. Piekarska-Boniecka.

Mazovian Lowland: [DC89] Kampinoski NP, Karczmisko, 17.09.2016 – 1♀ in pine forest, leg. M. Miłkowski; [EC21] Puszcza Kozienicka, Brzózka, 17.12.2016 – 1♀ in a hollow in an old lime tree, leg. M. Miłkowski.

Białowieża Forest: [FD84] Polana Żubrówka, 11.11.2016 – 1♀, under the bark of an oak pole, leg. M. Miłkowski; [FD94] Białowieżyński NP, forest compartment no. 288C/318A/B, 6.07.2004 – 1♀, 23.07.2004 – 1♀, leg. J. Gutowski; [FD94] Białowieżyński NP, forest compartment no. 318B, 11.05.2004 – 1♀, leg. J. Gutowski.

Kraków-Wieluń Upland: [CB72] Góry Towarne, 26.07.2012 – 1♂ on flowers of *Libanotis montana*, leg. BW; [CB90] Mirów, 06.07.2012 – 1♀, grassland with *Libanotis montana*, leg. BW; [DA15] Ojcowski NP, Prądnik Valley, 09.09.2014 – 1♀, on a wooden building, leg. BW; [DA16] Ojcowski NP, Ojców-Droga Zamkowa, 24.06.1995 – 1♀, leg. A. Klasa; [DA16] Ojcowski NP, Grodzisko, 15.07.2003 – 1♀, leg. BW; [DA16] Ojcowski NP, Pieskowa Skała, 21.09.2005 – 1♀ on leaves of tall herbs on forest edge, leg. BW.

Małopolska Upland: [DA28] Pogwizdów, 02.08.2012 – 1♂, on a meadow, leg. BW; [DA69] Góry Pińczowskie Zachodnie, 24.07.2008 – 1♂ on flowers of Apiaceae, leg. BW; [DA69] ‘Polana Polichno’ Res., 14.08.2008 – 1♀, xerothermic grassland on chalk, leg. BW.

Sandomierz Lowland: [DA83] Łętowice, 14.06.2004 – 1♀, leg. BW; [DA84] Wierzchosławice, 20.08.2016 – 1♂, leg. BW.

Western Beskidy Mts: [DV89] Kamionka Wielka, 560 m a.s.l., 31.08.2018 – 3♀♀ and 1♂ on wall of a wooden house, leg. BW.

Pieniny: [DV57] Pieniński NP, Zamczysko, 600 m a.s.l., 21.08.1995 – 1♂, leg. A. Klasa; [DV57] Pieniński NP, Sromowce Niżne, 04.07.2014 – 1♀ on a stone wall by the information centre, leg. BW.

Hockeria unicolor WALKER, 1834

Listed from Poland for the first time by SZCZEPAŃSKI (1959), and later by SZCZEPAŃSKI (1968), WIĄCKOWSKI (1978), KOLK (1982), and MICZULSKI (1980). Included in the checklist of Polish Chalcididae (WIŚNIEWSKI 1997). New records:

Mazovian Lowland: [DC46] Bolimowski LP, Grabie, 14.07.1994 – 1♀, 31.07.1993 – 1♂, leg. J.K. Kowalczyk.

Upper Silesia: [CA86] Bukowno, 08.07.2012 – 1♂ on flowers of *Onopordon*, leg. BW.

Malopolska Upland: [DB25] Przedborski LP, ‘Murawy Dobromierskie’ Res., 27.05.2005 – 1♀, leg. B. Soszyński.

Roztocze: [FA49] Józefów vicinity, 08.07.2006 – 1♀ & 1♂ in a clear-cut in pine forest, on leaves of *Populus tremula*, leg. BW; [FA78] Bełzec, 10.07.2006 – 1♂ on flowers of *Daucus carota* in a sand pit, leg. BW.

Psilochalcis benoisti (STEFFAN, 1948)

Listed from Poland for the first time by BOUČEK (1952). Included in the checklist of Polish Chalcididae (WIŚNIEWSKI 1997) as *Invreia benoisti* (STEFFAN, 1948). New record:

Baltic Coast: [CF46] Jastarnia, 20.06.1998 – 1♂ on flowers, dune belt on the sea coast, leg. R. Dobosz.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

My sincere thanks go to the staff of the Department of Natural History of the Upper Silesian Museum in Bytom (Poland) (USMB), other institutions, as well as all the private collectors for the loan of specimens of chalcid wasps for studies.

REFERENCES

- BOUČEK Z. 1952. The first revision of the European species of the family Chalcididae (Hymenoptera). *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae* 27, suppl. 1, 108 pp.
- BRISCHKE C.G.A. 1881. Die Ichneumoniden der Provinzen West- und Ostpreussen. *Schlussbericht Bericht des Westpreussischen Botanisch-Zoologischen Vereins* 4: 104–167.
- BRISCHKE C.G.A. 1888. Hymenoptera aculeata der Provinzen West- und Ostpreussen. *Schriften der Naturforschenden Gesellschaft in Danzig, Neue Folge* 7(1): 85–107.
- BRISCHKE C.G.A. 1889. Bericht über eine Excursion nach Steegen, auf der frischen Nehrung, im Juli 1888. *Schriften der Naturforschenden Gesellschaft in Danzig, Neue Folge* 7(2): 193–209.
- BURAKOWSKI B., MROCZKOWSKI M., STEFAŃSKA J. 1971. Chrząszcze, Coleoptera, Piśmiennictwo. *Katalog Fauny Polski* 23(1), Państwowe Wydawnictwo Naukowe, Warszawa, 183 pp.
- GAULD I., BOLTON B. (Eds), 1996. The Hymenoptera. Oxford University Press, New York, 332 pp.
- GIBSON G.A.P. 1993. Superfamilies Mymarommatoidea and Chalcidoidea, pp. 570–655, In: GOULET H., HUBER J.T. (Eds), Hymenoptera of the world: an identification guide to families. Agriculture Canada. Research Branch, Ottawa.
- KLEJDYSZ T., WENDZONKA J. 2017. *Chalcis biguttata* SPINOLA, 1808 (Hymenoptera: Chalcididae) nowy gatunek w faunie Polski. *Acta entomologica silesiana* 25(030): 214. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.848138>.
- KOLK A. 1982. Zjawisko konkurencji wśród endopasożytów gąsienic zwójki sosnoweczki (*Rhyacionia buoliana* SCHIFF.) i skośnika tuzinka (*Exoteleia dodecella* L.). *Zeszyty Problemowe Postępów Nauk Rolniczych* 251: 39–53.
- MICZULSKI B. 1980. Materiały do znajomości fauny błonkówek (Hymenoptera) upraw zbożowych w okolicach Lublina. *Roczniki Nauk rolniczych, seria. E* 10: 27–58.
- NIKOLSKAJA M. N. 1960. Chalcidy sem. Chalcididae i Leucospidae. Fauna SSSR, Pereponchatokrilyje, t. VII (5). Izdatelstvo Akademii Nauk SSSR, Moskva Leningrad, 220 pp.
- NOSKIEWICZ J., PUŁAWSKI W. 1974. Fauna słodkowodna Polski 9, 124 pp.
- NOYES J. S. 2018. Universal Chalcidoidea Database. World Wide Web electronic publication. <http://www.nhm.ac.uk/chalcidooids>
- SZCZEPAŃSKI H. 1959. Wyniki hodowli i połowu bleskotek (Chalcidoidea) na terenie Warszawy i bliskich okolic. *Zeszyty naukowe SGGW, Leśnictwo* 3: 105–116.
- SZCZEPAŃSKI H. 1968. Badania fauny bleskotek (Hymenoptera, Chalcidoidea) upraw i młodników sosnowych w nadleśnictwie Rogów koło Kuluszek. *Polskie Pismo entomologiczne* 38(4): 811–870.

- WIĄCKOWSKI S. 1978. Wpływ przemysłowych zanieczyszczeń powietrza na entomofagi skońnika tuzinka (*Exoteleia dodecella* L.) i mszyc oraz na inne owady występujące na sośnie w okolicy Tomaszowa Maz. *Folia Forestalia Polonica, series A-Forestry* 23: 175–187.
- WIŚNIEWSKI B. 1996. Nowe stanowiska bleskotek z rodzaju *Brachymeria* WESTWOOD, 1832 (Hymenoptera: Chalcididae) w Polsce. *Acta entomologica silesiana* 4(1–2): 29.
- WIŚNIEWSKI B. 1997. Chalcidoidea (bez Mymaridae), pp. 132–158, In: RAZOWSKI J. (Ed.), *Wykaz Zwierząt Polski*, 5. Wydawnictwo ISEZ PAN, Kraków.
- WIŚNIEWSKI B. 2000. Błonkówki (Hymenoptera) polskich Bieszczadów ze szczególnym uwzględnieniem Bieszczadzkiego Parku Narodowego. *Monografie bieszczadzkie* 8: 145–187.
- WIŚNIEWSKI B. 2007. Dodatki do fauny błonkówek (Insecta, Hymenoptera) Ojcowskiego Parku Narodowego. *Prądnik, Prace i Materiały Muzeum Szafera* 17: 131–148.
- WIŚNIEWSKI B. 2016. Katalog błonkówek (Arthropoda: Insecta: Hymenoptera) Ojcowskiego Parku Narodowego. *Prądnik, Prace i Materiały Muzeum Szafera* 26: 95–146.
- WIŚNIEWSKI B., DOBOSZ R. 1998. *Chalcis sispes* (LINNAEUS, 1761) (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) – nowy w faunie Polski gatunek bleskotki. *Wiadomości entomologiczne* 17(1): 55–58.

STRESZCZENIE

***Conura xanthostigma* (Dalman, 1820) – nowy w faunie Polski gatunek bleskotki oraz nowe dane o wybranych gatunkach Chalcididae znanych z pojedynczych stanowisk w Polsce (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea)**

Rodzina Chalcididae jest jedną z najmniej licznych pod względem liczby gatunków rodziną bleskotek w Polsce (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea). W opublikowanych pracach wykazano dotąd występowanie w kraju 12 gatunków tych błonkówek. Liczba obserwacji jest skąpa i wszystkie wykazane taksony znane są z pojedynczych stanowisk. W niniejszej pracy wykazano kolejny gatunek stwierdzony podczas prowadzonych badań, tj. *Conura xanthostigma* (DALMAN, 1820). Dwa osobniki zostały zebrane niezależnie przez autorów na Wyżynie Małopolskiej ([DA27] Rzeżuśnia by Gołcza, 26.07.2006 – 1 samiec, leg. BW) i na Wyżynie Krakowsko-Wieluńskiej ([CA97] Klucze, 11.08.2014 – 1 samica, leg. W. Żyła). Larwy tej bleskotki są zewnętrznymi parazytoidami larw rośliniarek z rodzaju *Arge* SCHRANK, 1802 (Hymenoptera: Argidae) rozwijających się na różach.

W pracy podano także nowe stanowiska ośmiu gatunków Chalcididae wykazanych wcześniej z Polski, a mianowicie: *Brachymeria femorata* (PANZER, 1801), *Brachymeria minuta* (LINNAEUS, 1767), *Brachymeria parvula* (WALKER, 1834), *Brachymeria tibialis* (WALKER, 1834), *Chalcis biguttata* SPINOLA, 1808, *Chalcis sispes* (LINNAEUS, 1761), *Haltichella rufipes* (OLIVIER, 1791) i *Hockeria bifasciata* WALKER, 1834.

Accepted: 1 March 2019; published: 29 March 2019

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